

Fault Detection and Fault Diagnosis in Power System Using AI: A Review

Syeda Faiza Nasim¹, Sidra Aziz², Asma Qaiser³, Umm-e-Kulsoom⁴, and Saad Ahmed⁵

¹Lecturer, Department of Computer Science, NED University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

²Instructor, Electronics Technology, Aligarh Institute of Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

³Lecturer, Department of Computer Science, Iqra University, Karachi, Pakistan

⁴Lecturer, Department of Computer Science, PAF Karachi Institute of Economics and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

⁵Professor, Department of Computer Science, Iqra University, Karachi, Pakistan

Correspondence Author: Syeda Faiza Nasim (sfaizaadnan@gmail.com; sfnasim@cloud.neduet.edu.pk)

Received August 15, 2023; Revised November 20, 2023; Accepted March 28, 2024

Abstract

Electricity, which is essential to modern society, necessitates a consistent and uninterrupted supply. Faults in power systems pose difficulties, highlighting the vital importance of fault identification and diagnosis. This review paper provides a concise overview of artificial intelligence-based fault detection and diagnosis in power systems. The primary focus is on deep learning; on the one hand, it compares various works and acts as a primer for those who are unfamiliar with them. On the other hand, it delves into the application of UV-visible video processing to detect incipient faults by analyzing corona discharge and air ionization. Moreover, this state-of-the-art work highlights deep learning applications, particularly in UV-visible video processing, with the goal of detecting incipient faults through corona discharge and air ionization analysis. Despite ongoing research, the field lacks a clear path and structure, emphasizing the need for continued advancement in utilizing AI for effective fault detection and diagnosis in power systems.

Index Terms: Artificial Intelligence, Computing Machines, Fault Detection, Fault Diagnosis, Electrical Power System.

I. INTRODUCTION

The most popular form of energy being used today is electrical energy. Modern society relies heavily on the continuous supply and availability of electrical power. From computers to telecommunications, from industrial users to domestic users, the importance of electrical power cannot be understated [1], and [2]. This further increases the demand for continuous power supply. It must be noted that no power system can be made so that it will never fail. Faults and failures are part of a system. The important thing is the prevention of these faults as much as possible and the mitigation of such faults [1]. 80% of faults occur in distribution lines; hence, this area is of particular importance for researchers [3]. Moreover, with the integration of renewable sources in the system like wind and solar, two-way power flows are introduced, adding to the complexity of a distribution system [4], and [5].

The paper focuses on distribution networks, so it only discusses faults in distribution networks and their effects. The Literature regarding fundamentals of power system protection by author Bhide, et al, is an excellent work on the protection of power systems and discusses different types of faults, their effects, and conventional methods for fault detection and mitigation [1]. Faults in the power system not only affect the supply of electrical power but can also cause serious accidents. With an emphasis on the high-level procedures and the algorithms utilized in each phase of power system fault detection, our abstract pseudo

code offers a succinct summary of the complete procedure. The fact that each function call denotes a distinct kind of fault detection, makes the system more abstract and visually clear.

Our review paper delineates various types of detection using pseudocode here in table I, providing a thorough overview of the subject.

A. Motivation

This review paper offers a thorough summary of current developments in AI-based power system malfunction diagnosis and detection. It efficiently combines data from several studies, providing a useful tool for practitioners and researchers in the field. The strength of this paper lies in its well-structured arrangement, lucid explanations, and incorporation of methodology and outcomes.

B. Contribution

Our review paper makes two contributions: first, it serves as a comprehensive primer on artificial intelligence-based fault detection and diagnosis in power systems, with a particular emphasis on deep learning methodologies, providing both an overview and comparative analysis of various works in the field. Second, the paper introduces a novel approach by emphasizing the practical application of deep learning, particularly in UV-visible video processing, for the detection of incipient faults via corona discharge and air ionization analysis. The effective application of deep learning techniques in this context is a significant

finding. While acknowledging the current lack of a clear path and structure in the field, the paper calls for continued research and development, positioning itself as a catalyst for advancements.

Table I: Types of Detection

Power System Fault Detection Abstract Pseudo Code
Incipient Faults Detection severity_levels = detect_incipient_faults (video_data)
Earth Fault Detection detected_faulty_feeders = detect_earth_fault (current_signals)
Islanding and Grid Fault Detection fault_types, deep_learning_results, bayesian_network_results = detect_islanding_and_grid_faults (system_data)
Fault Detection for DERs svdd_results, hisvdd_results, pca_results, ica_results = detect_faults_for_ders (der_data)
High Impedance Fault Detection stft_results, cnn_results, dwt_results, lstm_results, vpe_results, decision_tree_results = detect_high_impedance_faults (grid_data)
Insulator Fault Detection renn_results, mask_renn_results = detect_insulator_faults (image_data)
Series Arc Fault Detection rf_results, dnn_results, cnn_lstm_results, clustering_results, svm_results = detect_series_arc_faults (arc_data)

C. Paper Organization

The Structure of the paper is as follows: Section II deals with the reason why this study has been conducted. Section III offers comparative analyses of recent achievements in fault detection. Section IV discusses the review of various well-known research papers related to the domain of fault tolerance. Section V covers the data and findings of the paper discussed in the previous section. Section VI concludes the paper and the last section VII enlightens the future work and limitations of this research work.

II. PURPOSE OF THIS STUDY

With the recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) due to the availability of large data sets and computing machines capable of handling those data sets, AI is being used in more and more areas to achieve results that are not possible using conventional means [6-11]. One such field is electrical power. New strides are being made in the field of electrical power, and various ways are being looked into how AI can help us achieve our goals efficiently [12]. One such domain is fault detection in electrical systems [13]. Distribution networks are where the majority of electrical power systems failures take place [14], and [15]. As a result, new studies are being conducted daily to discover new ways to apply AI for improved defect identification and diagnosis [16].

The paper provides a brief review of efforts being made in this regard. The aim of this paper is to give the reader a basic overview of advancements in this domain. Various fault detection methods are mentioned in figure I, which are further elaborated in the methodology.

Figure I: Fault Categories

III. RELATED WORK

The main AI techniques used in power network FD are reviewed in this section, along with their benefits and drawbacks below here in figure II, highlighting the business scene, algorithm engine, data collection, and high-performance computing frame.

A. The Expert System

Expert Systems (ES) provide a scientifically grounded explanation for defect growth by combining deterministic information with sound logic [17]. Even with their advantages, ES has trouble managing complex or large-scale grids, and maintaining the knowledge base can be a laborious process. Moreover, ES shows a restricted ability to learn and tolerate errors. To address these constraints, advances have been made by adding fuzzy set theory, which improves fault tolerance. Nonetheless, the challenges of keeping up a knowledge base for large-scale power systems must be taken into account [18].

B. The Network of Bayes (BN)

Bayesian Networks (BN), which use probability theory to resolve ambiguity in fault identification, provide reliable diagnosis in circumstances of unclear data by finding causal linkages. BN, however, requires a significant amount of prior knowledge, and modeling dynamic grid systems is difficult [19]. The combination of upgrades and monitoring technology has demonstrated efficacy in forecasting possible fault occurrences. However, it is important to consider the difficulties associated with obtaining statistical samples for significant grid outages [20].

C. Synthetic Nervous System (ANN)

In order to identify defects, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) mimic the biological nervous system, exhibiting significant fault tolerance, generalization, fast thinking, and multiprocessing capacities [21]. Despite these benefits, the diagnostic method is opaque and necessitates a large number of representative samples. Enhancements to generalization include the use of an extreme learning machine. The challenges of using ANN in large-scale grid applications and interpreting the outcomes are taken into account [22].

Figure II: Artificial Intelligence Fault Diagnosis System-Based Overall Framework

D. Methods of Optimization

Optimization methods serve as the cornerstone for a mathematical model for defect detection, providing a rigorous mathematical foundation while remaining simple to implement and program [23]. Nevertheless, getting complete samples for a precise diagnosis presents difficulties. Continuous integration combined with genetic algorithms is an improvement approach. Notably, optimization techniques yield excellent diagnosis outcomes, either locally or globally, even when partial information is available [24].

E. The Multi-Agent System

The Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) provide resilient, scalable, and educational benefits by dividing the grid fault diagnosis process into separate agent groups. Nonetheless, there are difficulties with reasoning, learning, and cooperative problem-solving among agents. More research is considered needed, especially to improve agent thinking and solve hardware/software problems [25].

F. Technology of Information Fusion

Information Fusion Technology entails merging and analyzing numerous data sources for problem diagnosis, resulting in higher accuracy, fault tolerance, and real-time performance [26]. Its effectiveness is further increased by improvements like the application of fuzzy integral theory and wavelet technology. The difficulties in choosing good training cases need to be taken into account.

G. Theory of Rough Sets (RST)

Rough Set Theory (RST) provides great fault tolerance and adaptation to incomplete data by managing uncertainty in knowledge and analyzing partial data to find flaws. Lessons learned include the effects of missing or inaccurate critical data as well as the dimensional issue of "combined explosion". Reducing knowledge and integrating AI with other technologies are future themes [27].

IV. METHODOLOGY

Reviews of journal papers from the IEEE Xplore Digital Library were conducted. The search terms that were utilized were distribution, power system, AI, defect diagnosis, and fault detection. The filter's range lies between 2014 and 2023. The papers were taken into account using the number of citations and how pertinent they are to the subject.

AI approaches are used to identify errors, fault tolerance, and detection in power systems. This has been worked on and figured out by several authors. A few excellent papers and the AI technique that they used are described below in table II.

Table II: AI Techniques used for Different Faults Detection

FAULT TYPE	METHOD	DESCRIPTION
Incipient Faults In Power Lines	R-CNN	The research paper proposes a method for diagnosing incipient faults in power distribution lines using UV-visible videos captured by corona cameras. The method includes faster R-CNN for power equipment detection, color thresholding for UV section extraction, median filtering for UV noise elimination, and severity level estimation based on UV discharge area to equipment area ratio [2].
	LSTM	The article proposes an Adaptive Time-Frequency Memory (AD-TFM) cell embedded in Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to detect incipient faults in power distribution systems. The model, called the AD-TFM-AT model, uses learnable scale and translation parameters to detect faults in time and frequency domains [28].
Earth Fault	CWT & CNN	The research paper presents a novel method for detecting earth faults in resonant grounding distribution systems using Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). CWT constructs grayscale images of transient zero-sequence current signals, while CNN extracts and classifies features to identify faulty feeders. The method outperforms conventional methods like Adaboost and SVM, demonstrating better performance and robustness under various fault conditions and interference factors [29].
	SVM	The proposed method utilizes a Support Vector Machine (SVM) to efficiently detect islanding and grid faults in real-life photovoltaic plants. The SVM-based algorithm handles the dilemma of discriminating between islanding and grid fault events [30].

	Ensemble Method	The paper proposed a new framework based on an optimization-enabled weighted ensemble method that combines essential ML algorithms. In the proposed method, the system will select and compound appropriate ML algorithms based on Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) weights [31].
Islanding and Grid Faults	SVM	The paper presents a precision-based method for islanding and grid fault detection in active distribution networks using a Support Vector Machine (SVM). The method accurately detects islanding and grid faults, ensuring power quality and reducing the impact on power quality [4].
	LSTM	The proposed approach focuses on detecting islanding in wind and PV DGs using a novel deep-learning classifier based on a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network. The method extracts valuable features from voltage and current signals, analyzes them for the second harmonic, calculates symmetrical components, and applies a novel deep learning classifier [32].
	Bayesian Network	The paper presents Bayesian networks that are used to model the complex relationships between power system parameters and detect islanding conditions. These networks can provide probabilistic reasoning for decision-making in islanding detection [33].
Fault Detection for DERS	SVDD & HISVDD	The paper proposes a data-driven protection framework for distribution systems with varying penetration levels of distributed energy resources. The model uses Support Vector Data Description (SVDD) and vectors for training, incorporating new data and previous support vectors. Hybrid Incremental SVDD (HISVDD), is an online updating model that incorporates new data and previous support vectors to retrain the SVDD model and adapt to system changes [34].
	PCA & ICA	The paper proposed data-driven approaches, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Independent Component Analysis (ICA), to identify unusual patterns and outliers in DER data [35].
High Impedance Fault	STFT & CNN	The research paper proposes a sustainable deep learning-based approach for real-time high-impedance fault detection in power grids. It uses edge computing, a Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), and a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to analyze high-frequency components and classify feature maps into High Impedance Fault (HIF) and healthy classes. This approach reduces network latency and traffic, enabling faster and more reliable fault detection in power grids [36].
	DWT & LSTM	The paper proposed an LSTM approach to detect High Impedance Fault (HIF) in solar Photovoltaic (PV) integrated power systems. The three-phase high-frequency current signals during non-faulty and faulty conditions are used for feature extraction, employing the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) [37].
	1D VPE7 & DT	The paper presents 1D VPE (Voltage-Phase-Excursion) and the Decision Tree (DT) algorithm for HIF fault detection [38].
Insulator Fault	R-CNN	The paper presents an algorithm using deep learning to detect insulator self-detonation defects, using a Faster R-CNN target detection network, semantic segmentation, and a classification network [39].
	Mask R-CNN	The method in this paper involves the use of the Mask R-Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for automatic extraction of multiple insulators in the infrared images, followed by transfer learning and dynamic learning rate algorithm for training [40].
Series ARC Fault	RF & DNN	The paper employs Random Forest (RF) feature selection to identify specific arc features, reducing Gini impurity. Time-domain, frequency-domain, and wavelet packet energy analysis are used to extract arc features. These features are then input into a Deep Neural Network (DNN) for training, resulting in a comprehensive arc detection model for different load types [41].
	CNN-LSTM	The proposed method combines three-dimensional features and Convolutional Neural Network-Long Short Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) to detect arc faults in aviation cables. The method uses vibration series tests, cutting parallel tests, and wet arc trajectory parallel tests to analyze arc current signals under different loads [42].
	Clustering & SVM	The paper uses the CEEMDAN method to obtain arc fault current components, employing 16 feature indexes and a feature selection method. It also proposes a hierarchical clustering algorithm and a sensitive component selection strategy to eliminate redundant components. A strong discriminative feature library is constructed for series arc fault detection based on a Support Vector Machine (SVM) [43].

V. DATA AND RESULTS

- **Diverse Approaches**

The references use a wide range of approaches, such as corona detection, support vector machines, one-class classifiers, ensemble deep learning, and convolutional neural networks, demonstrating a rich diversity in methodologies [2].

- **Sophisticated Technologies**

The approaches show a dedication to using state-of-the-art instruments for defect detection by integrating sophisticated technologies including deep learning, ensemble approaches, and innovative classifiers [4].

- **Specific Applications**

Each reference addresses a specific difficulty in power system protection and fault detection, catering to various parts of power distribution and electrical fault identification [13].

- **Innovation**

Phrases such as "Revolutionary Approach" and "Innovative Ensemble Deep Learning Technique" imply a dedication to progressing the field and possibly introducing new approaches.

- **Application Context**

The references emphasize practical applications ranging from fault diagnosis in power distribution lines to islanding and grid fault detection, indicating a concern for real-world applicability [29]. As the research into AI-based fault detection and diagnosis in power systems yielded important results. The comparative evaluation of different approaches demonstrated the importance of deep learning, especially for UV-visible video processing. This method, which emphasized corona discharge and air ionization analysis, proved effective for detecting early-stage faults. The effective use of deep learning techniques in UV-visible data processing for fault detection is one of the main discoveries. The study emphasizes the field's early stages despite the encouraging results, and it calls for continued research and development for a more organized and

conclusive strategy for using AI in power system fault detection and diagnosis.

VI. CONCLUSION

For fault detection and in power systems, various AI approaches, including SVDD, HISVDD, CNNs, 1-D VPE, RNN-based LSTM, Mask R-CNN, and cloud-based CNN models offer useful capabilities. Each method has pros and cons of its own. By creating contours around typical data and recognizing deviations, SVDD and HISVDD offer reliable methods for defect identification and diagnosis. CNNs are excellent at analyzing spatial and image data and extracting the necessary characteristics for problem identification and diagnosis. While 1-D VPE efficiently represents features, RNN-based LSTM models effectively capture temporal relationships in data from the power system. Mask R-CNN makes it possible to locate faults precisely in images, while cloud-based CNN models take the benefit of scalability.

VII. LIMITATION AND FUTURE WORK

Only a handful of papers are reviewed. Moreover, the reviews do not provide in-depth analysis. The work should be extended to include further papers and the broad domain should be further classified [44-48]. The classification may be done based on the type of fault being detected, the power equipment of the network for which the fault is being detected, the AI method used, etc. This field is relatively new, and with the smart grid concept, it could potentially be the future of power systems all over the world [49, 50].

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to acknowledge all the hard work done by the team of authors. Furthermore, the authors have no affiliations with any organization or entity that might have a direct interest in the subject matter of this paper.

Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

All the authors mentioned above in the paper titled "Fault Detection and Fault Diagnosis in Power System Using AI" declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this research work.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

Funding

The authors have not received any financial support or benefits that could be perceived as influencing the outcomes presented in this paper.

References

- [1] Paithankar, Y. G., & Bhide, S. R. (2022). Fundamentals of power system protection. PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
- [2] Davari, N., Akbarizadeh, G., & Mashhour, E. (2020). Intelligent diagnosis of incipient fault in power distribution lines based on corona detection in UV-visible videos. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 36(6), 3640-3648.
- [3] Sun, J., Yang, Q., Xu, W., & He, W. (2022). A distribution line fault location estimation algorithm based on electromagnetic time-reversal method calculated in the finite difference time domain. *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 64(3), 865-873.
- [4] Baghaee, H. R., Mlakić, D., Nikolovski, S., & Dragicević, T. (2019). Support vector machine-based islanding and grid fault detection in active distribution networks. *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, 8(3), 2385-2403.
- [5] Lin, Z., Duan, D., Yang, Q., Hong, X., Cheng, X., Yang, L., & Cui, S. (2020). One-class classifier based fault detection in distribution systems with varying penetration levels of distributed energy resources. *IEEE Access*, 8, 130023-130035.
- [6] Ramos, C., & Liu, C. C. (2011). AI in power systems and energy markets. *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 26(2), 5-8.
- [7] Nasim, S. F., Qaiser, A., Abrar, N., & Kulsoom, U. (2023). Implementation of AI in Traffic Management: Need, Current Techniques and Challenges. *Pakistan Journal of Scientific Research*, 3(1), 20-25.
- [8] Israr, A., Ali, Z. A., Alkhamash, E. H., & Jussila, J. J. (2022). Optimization methods applied to motion planning of unmanned aerial vehicles: A review. *Drones*, 6(5), 126.
- [9] Chandio, H. R., & Memon, A. P. (2023). Time-Frequency Transformation Technique with Various Mother Wavelets for DC Fault Analysis in HVDC Transmission Systems. *Sir Syed University Research Journal of Engineering & Technology (SSURJET)*, 13(1).
- [10] Khan, A., Khuhro, A. A., Memon, A. A., & Memon, A. A. (2022). An Investigation to Reduce Electricity Bills using Inverter AC in Pakistan. *Sir Syed University Research Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 12(2), 07-12.
- [11] Nasim, S. F., Ali, M. R., & Kulsoom, U. (2022). Artificial intelligence incidents & ethics a narrative review. *International Journal of Technology, Innovation and Management (IJTIM)*, 2(2), 52-64.
- [12] Antonopoulos, I., Robu, V., Couraud, B., Kirli, D., Norbu, S., Kiprakis, A., ... & Wattam, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence and machine learning approaches to energy demand-side response: A systematic review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 130, 109899.
- [13] Elmasry, W., & Wadi, M. (2022). EDLA-EFDS: A novel ensemble deep learning approach for electrical fault detection systems. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 207, 107834.
- [14] Haleem, A. M., Sharma, M., Sajan, K. S., & Babu, K. D. (2018, June). A comparative review of fault location/identification methods in distribution networks. In *2018 1st International Conference on Advanced Research in Engineering Sciences (ARES)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [15] Aleem, S. A., Shahid, N., & Naqvi, I. H. (2015). Methodologies in power systems fault detection and diagnosis. *Energy Systems*, 6, 85-108.
- [16] Demirci, M., Gözde, H., & Taplamacioglu, M. C. (2023). Improvement of power transformer fault diagnosis by using sequential Kalman filter sensor fusion. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 149, 109038.
- [17] Kezunovic, M., Spasojevic, P., Fromen, C. W., & Sevcik, D. R. (1993). An expert system for transmission substation event analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 8(4), 1942-1949.
- [18] Lee, H. J., Park, D. Y., Ahn, B. S., Park, Y. M., Park, J. K., & Venkata, S. S. (2000). A fuzzy expert system for the integrated fault diagnosis. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 15(2), 833-838.
- [19] Teive, R. C. G., Coelho, J., Camargo, C. D. B., Charles, P. C., Lange, T., & Cimino, L. (2011, September). A bayesian network approach to fault diagnosis and prognosis in power transmission systems. In *2011 16th International conference on intelligent system applications to power systems* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [20] Zhang, X., Wei, J., Zhao, D., Zhang, D., & Liu, Y. (2013). Research course and prospects of power grid fault diagnosis. *Power System Technology*, 37(10), 2745-2753.
- [21] Wang, J. L., Xia, L., Wu, Z. G., Yang, X. F., & Li, Z. (2010). State of arts of fault diagnosis of power systems. *Power System Protection and Control*, 38(18), 210-211.
- [22] Xia, W., Zhang, L., Yuan, Q., Chen, G., Ma, S., Liu, Y., & Li, H. (2015). Improved extreme learning machine applied in power system fault diagnosis. *Power System and Clean Energy*, 31(4), 15-19.

- [23] Lin, X., Ke, S., Li, Z., Weng, H., & Han, X. (2010). A fault diagnosis method of power systems based on improved objective function and genetic algorithm-tabu search. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 25(3), 1268-1274.
- [24] Guo, W., Wen, F., Liao, Z., Wei, L., & Xin, J. (2009). An analytic model-based approach for power system alarm processing employing temporal constraint network. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 25(4), 2435-2447.
- [25] Refaat, S. S., Mohamed, A., & Kakosimos, P. (2018, April). Self-Healing control strategy; Challenges and opportunities for distribution systems in smart grid. In *2018 IEEE 12th International conference on compatibility, power electronics and power engineering (CPE-POWERENG 2018)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [26] Guo, C., You, J., Peng, M., Tang, Y., Liu, Y., & Chen, J. (2010). A fault intelligent diagnosis approach based on element-oriented artificial neural networks and fuzzy integral fusion. *Diangong Jishu Xuebao(Transactions of China Electrotechnical Society)*, 25(9), 183-190.
- [27] Shoupeng, W., & Dongmei, Z. (2017). Research Review and Prospects for Power Grid Fault Diagnosis [J]. *Automation of Electric Power Systems*, 41(19), 164-175.
- [28] Li, Q., Luo, H., Cheng, H., Deng, Y., Sun, W., Li, W., & Liu, Z. (2023). Incipient Fault Detection in Power Distribution System: A Time-Frequency Embedded Deep-Learning-Based Approach. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 72, 1-14.
- [29] Guo, M. F., Zeng, X. D., Chen, D. Y., & Yang, N. C. (2017). Deep-learning-based earth fault detection using continuous wavelet transform and convolutional neural network in resonant grounding distribution systems. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 18(3), 1291-1300.
- [30] Baghaee, H. R., Mlakić, D., Nikolovski, S., & Dragicević, T. (2019). Support vector machine-based islanding and grid fault detection in active distribution networks. *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, 8(3), 2385-2403.
- [31] Yavuz, L., Soran, A., Önen, A., Li, X., & Muyeen, S. M. (2021). Adaptive Fault Detection Scheme Using an Optimized Self-healing Ensemble Machine Learning Algorithm. *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, 8(4), 1145-1156.
- [32] Abdelsalam, A. A., Salem, A. A., Oda, E. S., & Eldesouky, A. A. (2020). Islanding detection of microgrid incorporating inverter based DGs using long short-term memory network. *IEEE Access*, 8, 106471-106486.
- [33] Najy, W. K., Zeineldin, H. H., Alaboudy, A. H. K., & Woon, W. L. (2011). A Bayesian passive islanding detection method for inverter-based distributed generation using ESPRIT. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 26(4), 2687-2696.
- [34] Lin, Z., Duan, D., Yang, Q., Hong, X., Cheng, X., Yang, L., & Cui, S. (2020). One-class classifier based fault detection in distribution systems with varying penetration levels of distributed energy resources. *IEEE Access*, 8, 130023-130035.
- [35] James, J. Q., Hou, Y., Lam, A. Y., & Li, V. O. (2017). Intelligent fault detection scheme for microgrids with wavelet-based deep neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 10(2), 1694-1703.
- [36] Sirojan, T., Lu, S., Phung, B. T., Zhang, D., & Ambikairajah, E. (2018). Sustainable deep learning at grid edge for real-time high impedance fault detection. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Computing*, 7(2), 346-357.
- [37] Veerasamy, V., Wahab, N. I. A., Othman, M. L., Padmanaban, S., Sekar, K., Ramachandran, R., ... & Islam, M. Z. (2021). LSTM recurrent neural network classifier for high impedance fault detection in solar PV integrated power system. *IEEE access*, 9, 32672-32687.
- [38] Xiao, Q. M., Guo, M. F., & Chen, D. Y. (2021). High-impedance fault detection method based on one-dimensional variational prototyping-encoder for distribution networks. *IEEE Systems Journal*, 16(1), 966-976.
- [39] Li, X., Su, H., & Liu, G. (2020). Insulator defect recognition based on global detection and local segmentation. *IEEE Access*, 8, 59934-59946.
- [40] Wang, B., Dong, M., Ren, M., Wu, Z., Guo, C., Zhuang, T., ... & Xie, J. (2020). Automatic fault diagnosis of infrared insulator images based on image instance segmentation and temperature analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 69(8), 5345-5355.
- [41] Jiang, J., Li, W., Wen, Z., Bie, Y., Schwarz, H., & Zhang, C. (2021). Series arc fault detection based on random forest and deep neural network. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 21(15), 17171-17179.
- [42] Liu, X., Huang, D., Jing, T., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Detection of AC arc faults of aviation cables based on HIW three-dimensional features and CNN-LSTM neural network. *IEEE Access*, 10, 106958-106971.
- [43] Zou, G., Fu, G., Han, B., Wang, W., & Liu, C. (2023). Series Arc Fault Detection Based on Dual Filtering Feature Selection and Improved Hierarchical Clustering Sensitive Component Selection. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 23(6), 6050-6060.
- [44] Zhang, Y., Wang, X., He, J., Xu, Y., Zhang, F., & Luo, Y. (2020). A transfer learning-based high impedance fault detection method under a cloud-edge collaboration framework. *IEEE Access*, 8, 165099-165110.
- [45] Guo, M. F., Liu, W. L., Gao, J. H., & Chen, D. Y. (2023). A data-enhanced high impedance fault detection method under imbalanced sample scenarios in distribution networks. *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*.
- [46] Dubey, K., & Jena, P. (2023). A Novel High Impedance Fault Detection Technique in Smart Active Distribution Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*.
- [47] Cui, L., Liu, Y., Wang, L., Chen, J., & Zhang, X. (2023). High-impedance fault detection method based on sparse data divergence discrimination in distribution networks. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 223, 109514.
- [48] Chandrakar, R., Dubey, R. K., & Panigrahi, B. K. (2023). Synchro-Squeezing Transform for High-Impedance Fault Detection in Power Distribution Systems. *IEEE Systems Journal*.
- [49] Kumar, R. S., Saravanan, S., Pandiyan, P., & Tiwari, R. (2023). Impact of artificial intelligence techniques in distributed smart grid monitoring system. In *Smart Energy and Electric Power Systems* (pp. 79-103). Elsevier.
- [50] Ucar, F. (2023). A Comprehensive Analysis of Smart Grid Stability Prediction along with Explainable Artificial Intelligence. *Symmetry*, 15(2), 289.